

Novel Benzothiophene Derivatives Derived from Fatty Acid Hydrazides: Synthesis and Evaluation of Antimycobacterial and Antimicrobial Potential

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Received: Apr 10, 2026

Accepted: May 8, 2026

Published: May 11, 2026

ABSTRACT:

The Novel substituted fatty acid hydrazides with benzothiophene derivatives have been synthesized by esterification of fatty acids followed by reaction of fatty acid ester with hydrazine hydrate to get fatty acid hydrazides. The 1, 3-chloro-1-benzothiophene-2-carbonyl chloride has been synthesized from substituted cinnamic acid with thionylchloride. The acid hydrazide was converted to (Z)-3-chloro-N'-benzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide (**Fa-h**) by condensation reaction. The synthesized compounds have been characterized by physical (melting point and TLC) and spectral analysis (FTIR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and Mass). All synthesized derivatives were screened for their antitubercular and antimicrobial activity.

Key words: Fatty acids, Benzothiophene, Acid hydrazides, Antimicrobial activity, Antitubercular activity.

INTRODUCTION:

One of the most significant public health issues of the twenty-first century is tuberculosis (TB), which is brought on by the bacteria *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*¹. TB is an endemic illness affecting every nation in the world, and mortality from it is more frequent than death from those other bacterial infections^{2,3}. About 5.5 million of the 9 million new cases and 1.5 million deaths from TB occurred in Asia, 1.5 million in Africa, 745,000 in the Middle East, and 600,000 in Latin America in 2013⁴. Moreover, 500,000 instances of MDR-TB (multidrug-resistant TB) are recorded year globally^{5,6} and up to 50 million people are sick with drug-resistant strains of the disease, making treatment challenging.

Although various anti-TB drugs (from first-line drugs to third-line drugs) were developed for the treatment of TB patients, they have showed the limit in reducing the current TB patients. Recently, compounds such as PA 824, SQ 109, bedaquiline, and linezolid repurposed through chemical remodeling of the existing drugs as well as new compounds such as Q203, TMC 207, pyridomycin, and thiophenes are being tested in Phase I or Phase III trials as novel anti-TB drugs^{7,8,9,10,11}. Until recently, in spite of the discovery of new targets and/or drugs for treating TB, the rapid emergence of TB, and multi-drug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) or extensively drug-resistant TB has still caused serious concerns in the public health field worldwide. For these reasons, various studies for developing the effective anti-TB drugs with novel mechanisms of action, low cytotoxicity and safety are urgently needed to block and/or to inhibit the TB¹².

Thiophene is a five-membered aromatic ring structure in the heterocyclic chemistry. It contains one sulfur atom as a heteroatom and four carbon atoms. Thiophene can extremely behave reactive like benzene in terms of having a pie electron cloud structure. The substituted thiophene derivatives are very well known for medicinal applications. Many substituted thiophene compounds have performed as chemotherapeutic and anticancer agents. For these reasons, substituted thiophene compounds were also applied successfully in other fields such as pharmacology, agriculture and industrial applications. These compounds were used in the development of agricultural products and in drug research since they have diverse biological activities. Some known activities are antitubercular¹³, analgesic & anti-inflammatory¹⁴,

antihypertensive¹⁵, anti-microbial¹⁶, antifungal¹⁷ and antineoplastic¹⁸ activities. Hence, they are popular targets for organic chemists.

Fatty acids are derived from renewable raw materials and exhibit various biological activities. Fatty acids also serve as a precursor for a variety of biological functions. Fat-soluble vitamins (vitamins A, D, E, and K) and carotenoids are involved in fat-transported pathways that regulate inflammation, coagulation, and gene expression¹⁹. Heterocyclic-fatty acid hybrid derivatives are a new class of heterocyclic compounds with a broad range of biological activities and significance in the field of medicinal chemistry.

In this aspect, this study was carried out to evaluate antimycobacterial and antimicrobial activity of fatty acid hydrazides condensed with bezothiophene ring that effectively act as bioactive substance, and to identify the potential for developing them as novel anti-tubercular and antimicrobial agents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

Varying materials used in this investigation were of analytical grade and purchased from SD fine and Aldrich. Melting point ranges was determined by arson Digital melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using BRUKER AV III, 400MHz FT-NMR Spectrometer, SAIF, and IIT Madras. IR spectra were recorded on Bruker Alpha FTIR Spectrophotometer with a universal sampling model using KBr pellets. MS spectra were recorded on 410 Prostar Binary LC with 500 MS IT PDA Detectors. TLC was carried out using precoated Silica gel plates.

Procedure for Synthesis of Thiophene Derivatives:

The pyridine (1 ml) and thionyl chloride (40 ml) were applied to the cinnamic acid substituents (cinnamic acid and 4-nitro cinnamic acid, 0.01 mole) was refluxed on water bath for 12 h and the excess thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The recognisable black sticky residue was acquired. A 500ml decant of boiling hexane was added to this. It was chilled and purified. Ultimately, a solid of yellow hue was produced.

General Procedure for Synthesis of Fatty Acid Esters:

A round bottomed flask with 35ml of ethanol and 10g of fatty acid was added, and then con. Sulphuric acid was added from the RBF's walls. The resulting mixture was allowed to cool after being refluxed for six hours. The resulting mixture was neutralized with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution that had been filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

General Procedure for Synthesis of Fatty Acid Hydrazides:

The fatty acid ester obtained in the previous step (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 hours with 4 ml of hydrazine hydrate. Ethanol (20ml) was added. After cooling, distilled water was added to dilute the reaction mixture. The resultant combination underwent filtration, distilled water washing, and recrystallization with ethanol.

Condensation of Fatty Acid Hydrazide with Thiophene Derivatives:

10 ml of pyridine and a thiophene derivative (0.001mol) were added to the fatty acid hydrazide (0.001mol) and stirred for an hour. The residue was treated with dil hydrochloric acid after the solvent was eliminated and filtered. Then it was recrystallized from the appropriate solvent after being rinsed with distilled water.

Compound Fa: (Z)-3-chloro-N'-oleoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide. Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 27%, m.p. 82-87°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm^{-1} :** 2919.7 cm^{-1} (Ar C-H str), 1681.6 cm^{-1} (C=C str), 1630.5 cm^{-1} (C=O str), 3315.0 cm^{-1} (N-H Str), 2848.06 (alkyl, C-H Str), 706 (C-Cl Str). **$^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) δ :** 0.82 (t, 3H, terminal CH_3), 5.24-5.28 (2H, m, -CH=CH), 2.10-2.18 (4H, m, - CH_2), 2.28 (2H, m, - CH_2) 1.42-1.77 (22 H, m, - CH_2), 7.53-7.80 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.22 (2H, dd, NH). **MS m/z:** 492 (M+1). Anal. Calcd for.: $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{39}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 66.03; H, 8.00; Cl, 7.22; N, 5.70; O, 6.52; S, 6.53. Found: C, 66.12; H, 8.08; Cl, 7.37; N, 5.78; O, 6.54; S, 6.62%.

Compound Fb: 3-chloro-N'-dodecanoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide. Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 39%, m.p. 47°C -50°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm^{-1} :** 2925.2 cm^{-1} (Ar C-H str), 1657.9 cm^{-1} (C=C str), 1620.7 cm^{-1} (C=O str), 3320.5 cm^{-1} (N-H Str), 2852.2 (alkyl, C-H Str), 725 (C-Cl

Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ**: 0.77 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.5-7.56 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.78-7.82 (2H, m, Ar-H) 2.13-2.18 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.35-1.54 (18 H, m, -CH₂), 8.4 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: C₂₁H₂₉ClN₂O₂S: C, 61.67; H, 7.15; Cl, 8.67; N, 6.85; O, 7.82; S, 7.84. Found: C, 61.52; H, 7.02; Cl, 8.25; N, 6.92; O, 7.54; S, 7.64%.

Compound Fc: 3-chloro-N'-palmitoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide. Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 36.5%, m.p. 72°C -77°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm⁻¹**: 2919.9 cm⁻¹ (Ar C-H str), 1683.6 cm⁻¹ (C=C str), 1628.6 cm⁻¹ (C=O str), 3325.2 cm⁻¹(N-H Str), 2852.2 (alkyl, C-H Str), 763.7 (C-Cl Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ**: 0.83 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.35-7.43 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.70 (2H, m, Ar-H) 2.30 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.15-1.51 (26 H, m, -CH₂), 7.92-7.99 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: C₂₅H₃₇ClN₂O₂S: C, 64.56; H, 8.02; Cl, 7.62; N, 6.02; O, 6.88; S, 6.89. Found: C, 64.72; H, 7.91; Cl, 7.42; N, 6.21; O, 6.79; S, 6.57%.

Compound Fd: 3-chloro-N'-stearoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide. Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 25%, m.p. 84°C -87°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm⁻¹**: 2924.2 cm⁻¹ (Ar C-H str), 1680.9 cm⁻¹ (C=C str), 1605.6 cm⁻¹ (C=O str), 3338.6 cm⁻¹(N-H Str), 2857.4 (alkyl, C-H Str), 780.2 (C-Cl Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ**: 0.78 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.42-7.49 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.57 (2H, m, Ar-H) 2.28 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.10-1.21 (30 H, m, -CH₂), 8.02-8.14 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: C₂₇H₄₁ClN₂O₂S: C, 65.76; H, 8.38; Cl, 7.19; N, 5.68; O, 6.49; S, 6.50. Found: C, 65.79; H, 8.45; Cl, 7.21; N, 5.60; O, 6.39; S, 6.71%.

Compound Fe: 3-chloro-6-nitro-N'-stearoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide. Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 47%, m.p. 102°C -105°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm⁻¹**: 2915.8 cm⁻¹ (Ar C-H str), 1691.3 cm⁻¹ (C=C str), 1598.7 cm⁻¹ (C=O str), 3224.4 cm⁻¹(N-H Str), 2848.4 (alkyl, C-H Str), 890.0 (C-Cl Str), 1523.5 (C-NO₂ Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ**: 0.76 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.65 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.90 (2H, m, Ar-H) 2.24 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.08-1.46 (29 H, m, -CH₂), 8.06-8.24

(2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: $C_{27}H_{40}ClN_3O_4S$: C, 60.26; H, 7.49; Cl, 6.59; N, 7.81; O, 11.89; S, 5.96. Found: C, 60.34; H, 7.42; Cl, 6.74; N, 7.87; O, 11.65; S, 5.91%.

Compound Ff: 3-chloro-6-nitro-N'-palmitoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide.

Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 40%, m.p. 70°C -75°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm^{-1} :** 2917.8 cm^{-1} (Ar C-H str), 1687.4 cm^{-1} (C=C str), 1597.7 cm^{-1} (C=O str), 3226.3 cm^{-1} (N-H Str), 2849.3 (alkyl, C-H Str), 878.4 (C-Cl Str), 1527.4 (C-NO₂ Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ :** 0.83 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.62 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.09 (2H, m, Ar-H) 2.16 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.28-1.48 (25 H, m, -CH₂), 8.24 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: $C_{25}H_{36}ClN_3O_4S$: C, 58.87; H, 7.11; Cl, 6.95; N, 8.24; O, 12.55; S, 6.29. Found: C, 58.80; H, 7.03; Cl, 6.86; N, 8.30; O, 12.50; S, 6.18%.

Compound Fg: (Z)-3-chloro-6-nitro-N'-oleoylbenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide.

Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 36.8%, m.p. 102°C -105°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm^{-1} :** 2917.8 cm^{-1} (Ar C-H str), 1630.6 cm^{-1} (C=C str), 1598.7 cm^{-1} (C=O str), 3317.0 cm^{-1} (N-H Str), 2849.3 (alkyl, C-H Str), 878.5 (C-Cl Str), 1530.2 (C-NO₂ Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ :** 0.83 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 6.90 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.34-7.48 (2H, m, Ar-H), 5.27 (2H, m, -CH=CH), 1.94 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.23-1.58 (25 H, m, -CH₂), 8.47 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: $C_{27}H_{38}ClN_3O_4S$: C, 60.49; H, 7.14; Cl, 6.61; N, 7.84; O, 11.94; S, 5.98. Found: C, 60.41; H, 7.23; Cl, 6.68; N, 7.67; O, 11.39; S, 5.90%.

Compound Fh: 3-chloro-N'-dodecanoyl-6-nitrobenzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide.

Recrystallized from ethanol to yield 28.7%, m.p. 92°C - 97°C. **FTIR (KBr) cm^{-1} :** 2918.7 cm^{-1} (Ar C-H str), 1630.5 cm^{-1} (C=C str), 1532.2 cm^{-1} (C=O str), 3316.0 cm^{-1} (N-H Str), 2848.8 (alkyl, C-H Str), 724.8 (C-Cl Str), 1468.5 (C-NO₂ Str). **¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ :** 0.83 (t, 3H, terminal CH₃), 7.16-7.23 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.44-7.50 (2H, m, Ar-H), 2.09 (2H, m, -CH₂), 1.18-1.46

(17 H, m, -CH₂), 8.27 (2H, dd, NH). Anal. Calcd for.: C₂₁H₂₈ClN₃O₄S: C, 55.56; H, 6.22; Cl, 7.81; N, 9.26; O, 14.10; S, 7.06. Found: C, 55.62; H, 6.18; Cl, 7.76; N, 9.20; O, 14.23; S, 7.19%.

Fig:1 Scheme: Conventional method for synthesis of substituted fatty acid hydrazides with Benzo-thiophene derivatives.

Anti-tubercular activity:

All newly synthesized compounds were screened for their anti-mycobacterial activity. Compounds was taken at concentration of 100 - 0.8 µg/ml against *M. tuberculosis* ATCC 27294 H37 Rv in middle brook 7H9 broth medium by serial dilution method was carried out in

department of microbiology, Belgaum institute of medical sciences, Belgaum. Compounds were screened at 100 – 0.8 µg/ml concentration in a broth micro-dilution assay with Alamar blue called as microplate Alamar blue assay^{20, 21} against *M. tuberculosis* ATCC 27294 H37 Rv to determine MIC. The results were comparisons with Pyrazinamide (3.125µg/ml), Streptomycin (6.25 µg/ml) and Ciprofloxacin (3.125µg/ml) as the reference drug and the test results, presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Anti-tubercular activity of 3-chloro-N'-benzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide (Fa-h):

Compound code	MIC, µg/ml							
	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.12	1.6	0.8
Fa	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
Fb	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Fc	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Fd	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fe	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Ff	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Fg	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
Fh	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R

S – Sensitive, R - Resistant

Antimicrobial activity:

The synthesized Novel substituted fatty acid hydrazide substituted Benzo-thiophene derivatives (**Fa-h**) were tested for their antimicrobial activity using four types of bacteria- *staphylococcus aureus*, *S.mutans*, *Escherichia coli*, *pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains by using serial dilution method²². The final compounds were tested at a concentration of 0.2 and 100 µg/ml respectively. Ciprofloxacin was used as a standard drug. The Results of antibacterial screening studies are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Antimicrobial study of 3-chloro-N'-benzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide (Fa-h):

Table 2a: MIC of synthesized compounds for *staphylococcus aureus*.

Code	Concentration (µg/ml)									
	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.12	1.6	0.8	0.4	0.2
Fa	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R

Fb	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fc	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Fd	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
Fe	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Ff	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fg	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
Fh	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R

Table 2b: MIC of synthesized compounds for *S.mutans*.

Code	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)									
	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.12	1.6	0.8	0.4	0.2
Fa	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fb	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fc	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fd	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fe	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Ff	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fg	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R
Fh	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R

Table 2c: MIC values of synthesized compounds for *Escherichia coli*.

Code	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)									
	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.12	1.6	0.8	0.4	0.2
Fa	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Fb	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Fc	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Fd	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Fe	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
Ff	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Fg	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Fh	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R

Table 2d: MIC values of synthesized compounds for *pseudomonas*.

Code	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)									
	100	50	25	12.5	6.25	3.12	1.6	0.8	0.4	0.2
Fa	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fb	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
Fc	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fd	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fe	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Ff	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R
Fg	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
Fh	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R

Std-Ciprofloxacin-2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, S – Sensitive, R – Resistant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A series of Novel substituted fatty acid hydrazide substituted Benzo-thiophene derivatives (**Fa-h**) was synthesized through a three step reaction. In step 1, 3-chloro-1-benzothiophene-2-carbonyl chloride **I** has been synthesized from substituted cinnamic acid with thionylchloride in the presence of pyridine. In step 2, fatty acid hydrazide **II** was prepared by ester of fatty acid was hydrazinolyzed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. In step 3 condensation of 3-chloro-1-benzothiophene-2-carbonyl chloride **I** with fatty acid hydrazide **II** in pyridine to form a title compounds (Z)-3-chloro-N'-benzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide (**Fa-h**). The structures of newly synthesized compounds were investigated according to their analytical and spectral data.

The IR spectrum of (Z)-3-chloro-N'-benzo[b]thiophene-2-carbohydrazide (Fa-h). Showed absorption bands around (N-H str) 3225 cm^{-1} , (C-H str) 2925 cm^{-1} , (alkyl, C-H Str) 2852.2, (C=C str) 1680.6 cm^{-1} , (C=O str) 1630.5 cm^{-1} . In $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra, all the products showed characteristic triplet signals in the region δ 0.82 ppm for terminal CH_3 protons of fatty acid. A multiplet at δ 7.20-7.80 ppm attributable to aromatic protons. The CH_2 protons of fatty acid chain appeared as a multiplet at δ 1.40-1.70 ppm. The NH protons appeared as double doublet at δ 8.20 ppm. A multiplet at δ 5.24-5.28 integrating for 2 olefinic proton ($\text{CH}=\text{CH}$) for the compound **Fa** respectively. Further confirmation was made on the basis of Mass and Elemental analysis data.

All the newly synthesized compounds (**Fa-h**) were screened *in vitro* for their anti-TB activity. The compound **Fd** showed excellent activity at 3.12 µg/ml greater than the standard. Whereas compounds **Fa & Fg** showed good activity at 12.5 µg/ml. The compounds **Fb, Fc, Fe, Ff** and **Fh** showed moderate activity at 25 µg/ml. The obtained results revealed that fatty acid moiety is a satisfactory backbone for significant anti-mycobacterial activity.

The title compounds **Fa-h** were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* strains by using serial dilution method. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined for the compounds. The MIC values from table 2a,2b reveals that compound **Fb, Ff** and **Fa** showed excellent activity active against two strains each of gram positive bacteria. The rest of the compounds found good to moderate active against *S. aureus* and *S. mutans*. Compound **Fa & Fb** showed maximum activity at 0.4 µg/ml against *P. aeruginosa*. Compounds **Fa & Fe** shows good activity against *E. coli*. The rest of the compounds were found to be good and moderately active against the tested microorganisms. The obtained results clearly demonstrate that this kind of compounds could be an effective antibacterial agent and the activity is depending on the chemical composition of the benzothiophene with fatty acid derivative.

CONCLUSION:

Novel substituted fatty acid hydrazide substituted Benzo-thiophene derivatives were synthesized, characterized by various analytical techniques and evaluated for their anti-microbial and anti-tubercular activities. Accrued results revealed that all of the tested compounds showed promising activity as antitubercular and antimicrobial agents. After all the above findings it can be concluded that bezothiophene ring and fatty acid hydrazides serve as a lead molecules for further modification to obtain a clinically useful novel entities.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The writers express their sincere gratitude to Creative Educational Society's College of Pharmacy, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh, India, for providing laboratory facilities, which enabled the successful and timely completion of this research project.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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